

Speech-to-Route: Leveraging Large Language Models for Taxi Route Visualization

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Abstract—Accurate interpretation of air traffic control (ATC) taxi instructions is critical for safe and efficient airport ground operations. This paper presents a Speech-to-Route (S2R) approach that automates the conversion of spoken taxi instructions into visualized routes. The S2R process comprises three key components: *Speech-to-Text (S2T)*, which transcribes spoken commands into text using the Wav2Vec 2.0 model; *Text-to-Concept (T2C)*, which extracts structured semantic representations from the transcribed text using the GPT-4.0 Mini model; and *Concept-to-Route (C2R)*, which maps the extracted information onto a node-link graph of the airport layout to generate taxi routes. The S2T module achieved a word error rate of 5.39% on a public ATC dataset and 9.78% on the Singapore Changi S2R dataset, outperforming Whisper-based models. In isolated evaluations, both the T2C and C2R modules achieved perfect performance, demonstrating their robustness in semantic parsing and route reconstruction. However, when integrated in the full pipeline, errors introduced during transcription propagated downstream, leading to a slight drop in overall performance: T2C achieved an overlap ratio of 0.934, and C2R successfully reconstructed 83.33% of taxi routes. This study introduces the first end-to-end S2R process that translates ATC commands into taxi routes. The proposed approach has the potential to enhance aviation safety and operational efficiency by reducing pilot workload, minimizing communication errors, and improving situational awareness. It also serves as a foundation for future advancements in automated air traffic management and intelligent airport navigation.

Keywords—Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding, Speech-to-Route, Large Language Models

I. INTRODUCTION

Navigating an aircraft between the gate and the runway presents a complex operational challenge for both air traffic controllers (ATCOs) and flight crews, particularly in challenging conditions such as low visibility, complex airport layouts, or unfamiliar airfields. Traditional taxiing procedures are mainly based on airfield signage, ground lighting, and ATCO verbal instructions. Although these methods serve as the backbone of current operations, they can become insufficient under adverse conditions, where miscommunication, ambiguity, or pilot workload can negatively impact operational safety and efficiency.

To address these challenges, various systems have been developed to enhance pilot guidance and improve situational awareness. One such system is Follow-the-Greens, a ground-based taxiing guidance solution that employs green navigation lamps installed on the centerlines or sidelines of taxiways

Figure 1: Speech-to-Route flowchart converting ATC commands into taxi routes. It consists of three modules: Speech-to-Text for transcribing spoken commands, Text-to-Concept for extracting structured semantic representations, and Concept-to-Route for constructing taxi routes. An integrated error check and feedback module enhances accuracy.

to guide aircraft along assigned routes. This system has demonstrated substantial benefits, including improved safety, reduced taxi times, lower fuel consumption, and decreased delays [1], [2]. However, the deployment of this system is limited to select airports, leaving many airfields without its advantages.

In addition to ground-based systems, aircraft-centric solutions such as Jeppesen’s Airport Moving Maps [3] and SESAR’s “A-SMGCS Routing and Planning Functions” project [4] have been developed. These solutions offer graphical representations of airport layouts with touchscreen interfaces for manual route entry. Although these tools improve situational awareness, they also introduce additional workload for pilots, requiring manual input during critical flight phases when cognitive demands are already high [4].

Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding (ASRU) offers a promising solution to address the challenges associated with ATC-pilot communication by automating both the transcription and interpretation of spoken instructions. ASRU generally consists of two primary components: Speech-to-Text (S2T), which converts spoken commands into written text, and Text-to-Concept (T2C), which extracts structured semantic representations from the transcribed text [8]. In aviation, ASRU has been integrated into various systems to

enhance efficiency and safety [5]–[7]. By leveraging ASRU, taxi route interpretation can be streamlined, reducing pilot workload while improving the accuracy and reliability of ground operations.

This paper introduces a novel Speech-to-Route (S2R) functionality that automates the conversion of ATC-issued taxi commands into visualized taxi routes, as conceptualized in Figure 1. It presents the first approach to route visualization from ATC commands, enabling real-time construction of navigable paths from spoken input. A comprehensive S2R pipeline is also introduced, combining advanced speech recognition, natural language processing, and route reconstruction algorithms. The key contributions include the development of a fully automated process that converts spoken ATC commands into precise, visualized taxi routes, offering a substantial improvement over current airside navigation systems. By integrating Speech-to-Text (S2T), Text-to-Concept (T2C), and Concept-to-Route (C2R) modules, this work establishes a new paradigm for generating routes from dynamic spoken commands. Additionally, an error checking and feedback (ECF) module specific to airport operations ensures that generated routes comply with operational standards, adding robustness. This research lays the foundation for future advancements in automated air traffic management, advancing the path toward fully autonomous systems for airport ground operations.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work, Section III describes data collection and analysis, and Section IV details the methodology. Section V presents the results, followed by Section VI, which outlines directions for future research. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Speech Recognition and Understanding in Aviation

ASRU offers a solution to the complex task of extracting actionable content from ATC-pilot communications. In the domain of Air Traffic Management (ATM), several ASRU-based systems have been developed to assist in automating and enhancing communication processes.

One notable example is AcListant®-Strips [5], which was designed to assist ATCOs by maintaining radar labels automatically. Building upon this, the HAAWAI framework [6] was developed to improve ASRU performance for similar applications, integrating AI technologies to streamline controller tasks. Another system, STARFiSH [7], incorporates ASRU into Advanced Surface Movement Guidance and Control Systems (A-SMGCS). STARFiSH reduces controller workload by automating the entry of information into the system, thereby enhancing both efficiency and safety.

Recent advancements, particularly in the HAAWAI framework, demonstrate that ASRU systems can achieve command recognition rates exceeding 90%, with no major safety concerns reported [8]. However, these systems are predominantly

Figure 2: A sample trajectory from the S2R dataset. The text represents the sequence of taxiway names, while the color indicates aircraft speed, with red denoting slower speeds and blue representing faster speeds.

rule-based, relying on predefined ontologies, command detection rules, and consistency checks that must be regularly updated. While these approaches perform well under normal conditions, their reliance on rigid rule sets poses limitations in non-standard scenarios. For instance, variations in phraseology, the use of non-English words, heavy accents, or atypical situations can significantly degrade performance. Addressing these challenges will require more robust, adaptable methods that can handle linguistic variability and unpredictable scenarios in real-world operations.

In the specific context of taxi instructions, prior work [9] explored a multitask learning architecture using Long Short-Term Memory networks to classify utterance intent and perform slot filling. This approach achieved near-90% accuracy, indicating the feasibility of generating digital taxi instructions from speech. However, several limitations are evident. The study does not incorporate a speech recognition component; rather, it processes input as one-hot encoded vectors, suggesting that the model operates on transcribed text rather than raw audio. Furthermore, the scope of the work is limited to demonstrating the feasibility of a T2C mapping, without proposing a practical application or downstream integration into navigational systems.

Recently, Large Language Models (LLMs) have been explored in the ATC domain [10], [11]. These models, trained on vast datasets, exhibit remarkable performance in handling linguistic variability and improving transcription accuracy, making them promising candidates for enhancing ASRU systems. This paper proposes leveraging LLMs to further enhance ASRU performance, contributing to the automation of ATC-pilot communications.

III. DATA ENGINEERING

A. Public Dataset

This subsection outlines the preparation of recorded voice data for training S2T models. The dataset, originally introduced in [11], is publicly available for download via the HuggingFace Hub¹. It consists of labeled data pairs, comprising ATC communication audio and corresponding transcripts, where each pair represents short utterances of approximately 10 seconds.

¹https://huggingface.co/datasets/AshtonLKY/augmented_audio_final

The raw dataset, totaling approximately 33 hours of audio, was constructed from four well-known open-source aviation datasets: ATCOSIM [12], ATC Complete [13], ATC Communication [14], and ATCO2 [15]. The processing pipeline involved data standardization, preprocessing, and cleaning to address inconsistencies in naming conventions, segmentation formats, and transcription quality across the original datasets. The complete details of these steps, including audio segmentation, transcript alignment, and cleaning processes, are described in [11].

The final dataset contains 24,444 audio-transcript pairs. To train the S2T model, the dataset was first split into training and test validation in a ratio of 8:2. For the training set, data augmentation including noise removal and speed modification is applied. As the result, the training set contains 53,766 samples, while the validation set comprises 3,778 samples.

B. Changi Airport Dataset

This subsection details the development of a specialized dataset for the S2R pipeline at Changi Airport, Singapore (ICAO: WSSS). Each sample comprises four key components: an audio recording of an ATC navigation command, its corresponding text transcription, a sequence of taxiways representing the intended route, and the associated aircraft trajectory. An example trajectory is depicted in Figure 2, with its corresponding label stored in JSON format, as shown in Listing 1. Due to the labor-intensive nature of manual labeling, the dataset is limited to 48 samples and is utilized exclusively for model evaluation. The small sample size of 48 samples is not a major concern as this dataset serves as a proof of concept for the S2R pipeline. The samples are collected from Changi Airport, ensuring high relevance and consistency for evaluating the core components of the approach. While a larger dataset would enhance generalization, this limited dataset is sufficient for validating the functionality of the pipeline in its current scope. Future research will expand the dataset to improve robustness and scalability.

Listing 1: JSON structure for a sample from the S2R dataset. The "id" field links the entry to its corresponding audio file and trajectory.

```

{id": "0012",
"command": "SIA12, CLEARED TO TAXI TO RUNWAY
20C, TAXI VIA V, V7 TO W, RIGHT ON Q",
"spoken": "Singapore One Two, cleared to taxi
to Runway Two Zero Center, taxi via Victor
, Victor Seven to Whiskey, right on Quebec
",
"parsed": {"callsign": "SIA12",
"instructions": {"destination": "Runway 20C"
, "route": [{"", "V"}, [{"", "V7"}, [{"",
"W"}, [{"RIGHT", "Q"}]}}
```

The dataset construction begins with modeling Changi Airport's airside network, which comprises three runways, 68 taxiways, and 240 gates, as a node-link graph $\mathcal{G}(N, E)$. In this graph, nodes represent intersections or endpoints, and edges correspond to taxiways and runways, as illustrated in Figure 3. The graph was constructed using the OSMNX module [16] with OpenStreetMap data and includes 1,058 nodes and

1,435 edges. Additional refinements were applied by removing irrelevant or minor features to focus on significant infrastructure elements. Aircraft trajectories were extracted from A-SMGCS data (Feb–Apr 2018), provided by the Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore, offering high-frequency position and velocity information. A map-matching algorithm [17], [18] aligns these trajectories with the airport's surface network using spatial and temporal matching. Spatial matching reduces noise by linking aircraft positions to taxiway segments, while temporal matching refines transitions with timestamps and velocity data, offering a detailed depiction of variable-speed aircraft movements.

Figure 3: The airside network of Singapore Changi Airport, with blue edges denoting taxiways and black edges representing runways. Runways 02L and 02C are designated for northbound traffic, while runways 20C and 20R accommodate southbound traffic.

The next step involves route selection and the transformation of controller commands. After map-matching, runway usage patterns at Changi Airport were analyzed, showing that Runways 02L/20R are primarily used for arrivals, while Runways 02C/20C handle most departures. Based on the patterns, the dataset includes departure routes only from Runways 02C/20C and arrival routes exclusively from Runways 02L/20R, organized into terminal-to-runway pairs. For each pair, 6 arrival and 6 departure routes are randomly selected, creating a dataset of 48 representative routes.

Expert pilots and air traffic controllers generated controller commands for these routes based on predefined assumptions: (1) taxi clearances are issued as complete, single instructions rather than incrementally; (2) hold short instructions are excluded due to a lack of data on crossing traffic; and (3) runway exit points are predetermined by controllers, eliminating pilot discretion. To enhance realism, the commands include variations in phrasing to reflect authentic communication dynamics. These commands were then converted into spoken language, with corresponding audio files generated using

Narakeet², a platform offering over 100 English voice options in various accents, including British, American, Canadian, Scottish, Australian, and Indian. This process ensures the dataset realistically mirrors real-world ATC scenarios, providing a robust foundation for system performance evaluation.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The Speech-to-Route (S2R) process, as depicted in Figure 1, automates the conversion of spoken ATC commands into taxi routes. It consists of three main modules: Speech-to-Text (S2T), Text-to-Concept (T2C), and Concept-to-Route (C2R). The S2T module transcribes spoken commands into text using an advanced speech recognition model to accurately capture the communication. The T2C module processes the raw text to extract structured semantic representations, converting it into sequences of taxiway names for machine interpretation. The C2R module maps these sequences onto the airport’s surface network using a node-link graph, generating a precise visualized route. An integrated error check and feedback (ECF) mechanism ensures route accuracy and consistency. The final output is a route directly usable by airside navigation systems, improving operational efficiency and safety.

A. Speech to Text

The Speech-to-Text (S2T) module transcribes spoken ATC commands into raw text, a critical step in converting spoken language into structured data. The Wav2Vec 2.0 model [19], a self-supervised model developed by Facebook AI, is employed for this task. It learns directly from raw audio waveforms, making it highly effective for domain-specific tasks, particularly in environments with limited labeled data. The model’s architecture is composed of a convolutional feature encoder, a masking mechanism, and a Transformer, which together ensure robust performance in noisy conditions typically encountered in ATC communications.

To enhance its performance for aviation-specific terminology, the model is fine-tuned using a specialized ATC dataset (Section III-A). Fine-tuning is conducted on two NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs with 32 GB of video memory. The hyperparameters, as outlined in Table I, are optimized to balance model accuracy and computational efficiency based on the available resources.

After the fine-tuning process, the model’s performance is validated using word error rate (WER) metric on both the ATC validation set and the Changi S2R dataset. Additionally, the model’s performance is compared to Whisper-based models, which were also fine-tuned for the same task, as detailed in [10], [11].

B. Text to Concept

The Text-to-Concept (T2C) module converts the transcribed text generated by the S2T step into structured semantic representations. This module interprets the ATC commands and converts them into machine-readable formats, enabling subsequent processing and visualization. For this task, the GPT-4.0 Mini model is used as a natural language

²<https://www.narakeet.com/app/text-to-audio>

Hyperparameters	Value
Train Samples	53,766
Val Samples	3,778
Batch Size	12
Epochs	10
Max Steps	44,800

TABLE I. The hyperparameters used in fine-tuning process for Wav2Vec 2.0 model.

processing engine to parse aviation commands into a structured JSON format. The model is prompted with specific instructions to ensure accurate parsing of the commands. The input prompt specifies the required output format, which includes structured fields such as the callsign, instructions, destination, and route. An example of the prompt is shown in Figure 4.

The parsing process is automated using the OpenAI API, which interfaces with the GPT-4.0 Mini model. The Python implementation sends the command prompt as input and receives the structured JSON response.

Figure 4: Prompt for the GPT-4.0 Mini model: The model converts a taxi instruction command into a structured JSON output.

Parse the following aviation command into a structured JSON format.

Command: "{command}"

The JSON output must follow this structure:

```
{
  "command": "<original command>",
  "parsed": {
    "callsign": "<callsign>",
    "instructions": {
      "destination": "<destination>"
    },
    "route": [ "<direction>", "<name>" ]
  }
}
```

<name> must consist of an alphabet character, optionally followed by a number (e.g., "WHISKEY FIVE" becomes "W5").

<direction> can be empty or contain directions such as "LEFT," "RIGHT," or "STRAIGHT."

C. Concept to Route

The Concept-to-Route (C2R) module translates the parsed taxiway names, generated by the T2C module, into a complete route between the gate and runway. This module bridges the gap between high-level ATC instructions and a detailed node-level route that aligns with the airport’s airside network. The

process involves reconstructing the route on the node-link graph of Changi Airport while addressing several challenges inherent to the data and the airport network structure.

- **Non-1-to-1 Mapping Between Taxiway Names and Nodes.** The relationship between taxiway names and nodes is not straightforward. A single taxiway can contain multiple nodes, and a single node may belong to multiple intersecting taxiways. This ambiguity complicates the process of precisely determining the path corresponding to each taxiway name in the sequence.
- **Unnamed Nodes.** Approximately 20% of the nodes in the airside network lack associated names. These unnamed nodes are often located at intersections or junctions between taxiways, making it challenging to seamlessly connect the sequence of taxiway names into a continuous route.
- **Discontinuous Taxiway Sequences.** ATC commands often omit intermediate taxiway names, leading to sequences that are not directly connected in the network. This requires the C2R algorithm to intelligently infer and fill in the missing links to ensure the final route is valid and navigable.

The route construction algorithm translates the sequence of taxiway names into a complete and navigable path using the node-link graph representation of the airport network. It iteratively finds connections between the nodes corresponding to taxiways in the sequence while addressing unnamed nodes and discontinuities. Below is a detailed step-by-step description, followed by Algorithm 1.

- 1) **Initialize Starting Nodes:** Identify all nodes associated with the starting point (either a gate or a runway). Denote this set as N_0 .
- 2) **Identify Target Nodes:** Find all nodes associated with the next taxiway in the sequence. Denote this set as N_t .
- 3) **Search for Connections:** Identify all taxiways T_1 directly connected to N_0 . A taxiway is connected if at least one of its nodes has an edge to a node in N_0 . Form N_1 by collecting all nodes belonging to T_1 , and all unnamed nodes connected to T_1 .
- 4) **Find Shortest Paths:** If N_1 is connected to N_t , use Breadth-First Search (BFS) to find the top k shortest paths between N_1 and N_t .
- 5) **Expand the Search if Necessary:** If no connection exists between N_1 and N_t , repeat the process:
 - a) Find all taxiways connected to N_1 , forming T_2 .
 - b) Form N_2 by collecting all nodes belonging to T_2 , and all unnamed nodes connected to T_2 .
 - c) Continue iterating (N_2 , N_3 , etc.) until a connection is found or the processing time exceeds a predefined threshold.
- 6) **Move to the Next Taxiway:** If a path is found, update N_0 to the nodes in N_t and repeat the process for the next taxiway in the sequence.

This process ensures that the route is continuous, even when intermediate taxiway names are missing or nodes are unnamed.

Algorithm 1: Route Construction Process

```

Initialize route  $R \leftarrow []$ ;
Set starting nodes  $N_0$ ;
foreach Taxiway  $T_i \in T$  do
    Find all nodes corresponding to  $T_i$ :  $N_t$ ;
     $k \leftarrow 1$  (iteration counter);
    while no connection between  $N_{k-1}$  and  $N_t$  and
        elapsed time  $< \tau$  do
        Find all taxiways connected to  $N_{k-1}$ :  $T_k$ ;
        Find all nodes belonged to  $T_k$  and all
            unnamed nodes connected to  $T_k$ :  $N_k$ ;
         $k \leftarrow k + 1$ ;
    if connection exists between  $N_{k-1}$  and  $N_t$  then
        Find top  $K$  shortest paths from  $N_{k-1}$  to  $N_t$ 
            using BFS;
        Append the shortest path to  $R$ ;
        Update  $N_0 \leftarrow N_t$ ;
    else
        return "No valid path found within threshold
            time";
return  $R$ ;

```

D. Error Check and Feedback

To prevent errors from propagating through the pipeline, an error check and feedback (ECF) module is integrated into the system. This module applies domain-specific knowledge, tailored to Changi Airport, to validate and refine the outputs at each stage of the pipeline. The validation process follows a set of predefined rules that ensure consistency and correctness in line with aviation standards and Changi Airport’s operational guidelines:

- **Runway Naming Rules:** Changi Airport uses exactly six runway designations, combining the numeric identifiers “02” and “20” with the suffixes “L”, “C”, and “R” for left, center, and right, respectively.
- **Taxiway Naming Rules:** Taxiway names consist of a single alphabetic character, optionally followed by numeric digits.
- **Default Runway Holding Position and Rapid Exit Taxiway:** If no explicit holding position or rapid exit is specified, default names will be assigned based on each runway.
- **Valid Taxiway Names:** Taxiway names not associated with Changi Airport are excluded from the dataset.

These rules help identify any inconsistencies or errors in the outputs, enabling immediate correction and maintaining the accuracy of the pipeline. This error-checking mechanism minimizes the risk of cascading errors and ensures the system’s reliability in real-world applications.

V. RESULTS

A. Speech to Text

The performance of the proposed model was evaluated by comparing its word error rate (WER) with two Whisper-based

Models	ATC	Changi S2R
Whisper-ATC [10]	13.46%	-
Whisper [11]	6.12%	-
Proposed model	5.39%	9.78%

TABLE II. Comparison of the proposed model with Whisper-based models on the ATC dataset, along with the performance of the proposed model on the Changi S2R dataset. The evaluation metric used is word error rate, where lower values indicate better performance.

Ground Truth	Prediction
center	cinter, centar, sent, senner, sentor, centor, sento
exit	ex it, exi, exat, axite, exbet
gate	gait, gat, goate, gap
two	to, too
four	for
five	fy

TABLE III. Sample mistakes of S2T model.

models [10], [11] on the validation set of the ATC dataset, as shown in Table II. The Whisper-based models achieved WERs of 13.46% and 6.12%, respectively. In contrast, the proposed model demonstrated an improvement, achieving a WER of 5.39% on the same dataset. This result highlights the effectiveness of the proposed model in transcribing ATC communications accurately, particularly in handling the specialized vocabulary and acoustic conditions inherent in air traffic control transmissions.

Additionally, the proposed model was validated on the Changi S2R dataset, which was not used during the training phase of the model. Despite this, the proposed model performed robustly on this dataset, achieving a WER of 9.78%. This result further demonstrates the model’s generalizability to different airside environments, such as the Changi Airport S2R dataset, even though it was not specifically fine-tuned for this dataset.

While the proposed model performs well overall, some sample mistakes were identified as shown in Table III, highlighting areas where further refinement could be made. These sample mistakes highlight the model’s challenges with certain phonetic similarities and variations in speech, emphasizing the need for further adaptation to specific accents and speech patterns common in the air traffic control domain. Nonetheless, the overall performance of the proposed model remains promising, demonstrating its potential to improve the accuracy and efficiency of ATC communication transcription.

B. Text to Concept

The performance of the T2C model was evaluated by comparing the extracted sequence of taxiway names (denoted as Seq_{pred}) with the ground truth sequence (denoted as Seq_{true}). The validation metric used for this comparison was the overlap ratio, calculated as:

$$\frac{||Seq_{pred} \cap Seq_{true}||}{||Seq_{true}||}$$

A result of 1 indicates that the two sequences are identical, while a result of 0 indicates that the sequences are completely different.

When using the spoken ground truth as input to the T2C model, the model achieved a perfect match, with an overlap result of 1, meaning it could extract the route perfectly from the ground truth. This indicates the model’s high capability to accurately convert the spoken commands into the correct taxiway sequence under ideal conditions.

However, when the T2C model received the output from the S2T model as input, the result was slightly lower, with an overlap of 0.934. Moreover, out of 48 test cases, 32 cases achieved a perfect overlap of 1. The remaining 16 cases exhibited errors that included missing taxiway names, adding extraneous taxiway names, or misinterpreting taxiway names entirely. These errors highlight the cascading impact of inaccuracies from the S2T module on the overall pipeline performance.

Despite these challenges, the T2C model demonstrated resilience by maintaining a high overlap rate of 0.934 when utilizing the imperfect S2T-generated text. Improvements to the S2T module could further enhance the reliability of the T2C extraction process and the overall S2R pipeline.

C. Concept to Route

To validate the C2R results, we compare the sequence of extracted taxiway names with the reconstructed taxi routes. A reconstruction is considered successful if the generated route passes through all the expected taxiway names.

When using Seq_{true} as input, the algorithm successfully reconstructed all routes. However, in many cases, Seq_{true} skipped two consecutive taxiways, particularly when they were near gates. This indicates that even the ground truth sequences may not always provide complete taxiway coverage, requiring the reconstruction algorithm to account for potential omissions.

When using Seq_{pred} , a preprocessing step was applied to normalize the routes. First, the destination needed to be valid. For departures, if the assigned runway was invalid, the system attempted to reconstruct the route using the nearest valid holding position. If neither the runway nor the holding position was correct, the reconstruction failed. For arrivals, if the assigned gate was invalid, the reconstruction failed entirely, as no meaningful route could be derived. Out of 16 error cases, 5 samples failed due to invalid destinations (either invalid runways or gates). Among the remaining 11 error cases, 3 samples failed to reconstruct while 8 samples were successfully reconstructed despite discrepancies in the predicted taxiway sequence.

For the 32 cases where Seq_{pred} matched the ground truth perfectly, the reconstruction was always successful. In total, the C2R algorithm successfully reconstructed 40 out of 48 routes, achieving an overall reconstruction success rate of 83.33%.

D. Case Study

1) *Failed Case: Misinterpretation of Taxiway Identifier:*
In this failed case, the ATC-issued command was: "Singapore Eight Zero One, exit Whiskey Four, right on Whiskey, to Gate Charlie One via Victor Five." The ground truth sequence

Figure 5: Failed Case Due to Misinterpretation of Taxiway Identifier: "V5" was misrecognized as "V".

(*Seq_true*) for this command was: ['02L', 'W4', 'W', 'V5', 'C1'].

The S2T model initially transcribed the command as: "singapore eight zero one exbet whiskey four right on whiskey togate charlie one via victorfy." After applying ECF mechanisms, the refined output became: "Singapore Eight Zero One, exit Whiskey Four, right on Whiskey to Gate Charlie One, via Victor." This resulted in the predicted taxiway sequence (*Seq_pred*) of: ['02L', 'W4', 'W', 'V', 'C1']. The deviation of "V" from the correct "V5" led to a failure in route reconstruction, as shown in Figure 5. Since "V" is a main taxiway, it connects with multiple other taxiways, significantly increasing the search space. As the number of possible connections grows exponentially, the algorithm fails to link "V" to "C1" within the time constraint.

2) *Successful Case Despite S2T Error*: In this successful case, the ATC spoken command was: "Jetstar Two Zero Six, exit Whiskey Five, cleared taxi to Gate Charlie Two Three via Whiskey, Victor Six, left on Victor to Victor One Three." The ground truth sequence (*Seq_true*) for this command was: ['02L', 'W5', 'W', 'V6', 'V', 'V13', 'C23'].

The S2T model initially transcribed the command as: "jetstar two zero six exit whiskey five cleared taxi to gape charlie two three via whiskey victor six left own victor to victor one free." After applying ECF mechanisms, the refined output became: "Jetstar Two Zero Six, exit Whiskey Five, cleared to taxi to Gate Charlie Two Three, via Whiskey, Victor Six, left on Victor to Victor One, free." This resulted in the predicted taxiway sequence (*Seq_pred*) of: ['02L', 'W5', 'W', 'V6', 'V', 'V1', 'C23']. Due to the misinterpretation of "Victor One Three" as "Victor One," the algorithm could not find a direct connection from "V" to "V1" within the time constraint as shown in Figure 6. As a result, "V1" was skipped. However, by linking "V" directly to "C23," the reconstructed route naturally passed through "V13" as the shortest path, making the reconstruction successful despite the transcription error.

VI. FUTURE WORKS

A. Generalizability Across Airports

The S2R pipeline is designed with generalizability in mind. Its core modules—S2T, T2C, and C2R—are developed independently of airport-specific data, enabling deployment across various airport environments without retraining. In particular, the S2T model is trained on a diverse ATC dataset rather than Changi-specific recordings, and the T2C module

Figure 6: Successful Case Despite S2T Error. Although "V13" was misrecognized as "V1", the algorithm could not establish a connection between "V" and "V1" within the time constraint, leading to the omission of "V1". Instead, "V13" was reconstructed as the connecting link between "V" and "C23"

uses a zero-shot approach via GPT-4.0 Mini, making it robust to differences in phraseology and traffic volume.

To support adaptation to specific airports, only the ECF module requires customization. This component ensures route compliance with local procedures, such as valid taxiway transitions or restricted areas. By isolating airport-specific logic to the ECF module, the pipeline remains largely portable and scalable, allowing efficient deployment to other major hubs with minimal configuration. To further validate this generalizability, the S2R pipeline will be tested on data from an additional international airport in future work.

B. Human-in-the-Loop Evaluation

Building on the S2R pipeline, the next phase involves a human-in-the-loop (HITL) study to evaluate a working prototype of an Electronic Flight Bag (EFB) application. This prototype supports multiple input modalities for taxi clearance input methods including S2R, map-touch, keyboard and conventional paper-based entry [22]. Pilots will interact with the EFB in a simulation environment to assess both the technical performance of S2R and its operational impact on pilot workload, usability, situational awareness, and trust, especially under degraded conditions and during clearance changes.

While the current focus is on aircraft-centric tools, future work may extend to ground-side interfaces for ATCOs, enhancing shared situational awareness without adding complexity to existing workflows. In the longer term, S2R-generated data could contribute to broader automation efforts, such as surface flow management or integration with trajectory planning systems like AMAN/DMAN [23], though these directions remain outside the scope of the current HITL study.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel approach to automating the translation of ATC-issued taxi instructions into visualized taxi routes. The process consists of Speech-to-Text, Text-to-Concept, and Concept-to-Route modules, with the goal of reducing pilot workload, minimizing communication errors, and improving situational awareness during taxi operations.

The proposed S2T model demonstrated superior transcription accuracy compared to Whisper-based baselines, achieving a lower word error rate on both a public ATC dataset and

an unseen Changi S2R dataset. The T2C module exhibited near-perfect performance when processing spoken ground truth, with minor degradation when using transcriptions from the S2T module. Finally, the C2R module successfully reconstructed 83.33% of taxi routes, even in cases where errors from the upstream modules introduced deviations. Case studies highlighted both failure and success scenarios, demonstrating the robustness of the reconstruction algorithm despite transcription errors. The proposed pipeline offers strong potential for generalization across airports, as the core modules are not trained on airport-specific data. To validate real-world applicability, an upcoming HITL study will evaluate the system within an EFB prototype, assessing usability, trust, and operational value in realistic simulation environments.

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